

Hybrid Diesel Microgrid Components

Considerations, Procurement, and Relevant Standards

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This technical report summarizes recommendations compiled from Alaska energy experts through the University of Alaska Fairbanks Alaska Center for Energy and Power (ACEP)-led Microgrids in Alaska Group: Photovoltaic Integration (MAGPI), and serves as a reference when considering how to integrate renewables in an Alaska diesel-based microgrid. These microgrids are not connected to larger grids and are thus permanently islanded, and some considerations may differ from those for islandable microgrids connected to a larger grid.

These recommendations have been heavily influenced by contributions from the Alaska Village Electric Cooperative (AVEC), particularly Aimie Survant and Bill Thomson. AVEC provides electric service to 59 rural communities across Alaska and has more power plants than all other electric cooperatives in Alaska combined¹. Their expertise in operating permanently islanded microgrids in Alaska was invaluable for preparing this document. Additional recommendations have been adapted from IEEE standards 1547 and 2030 for an Alaska microgrid context.

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¹ <https://avec.org/about/our-cooperative/>

Glossary of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AC	alternating current
ACEP	Alaska Center for Energy and Power
AVEC	Alaska Village Electric Cooperative
BESS	battery energy storage system
DC	direct current
°F	degrees Fahrenheit
GFL	grid-following (inverter)
GFM	grid-forming (inverter)
HOMER	Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources
HVAC	heating, ventilation and air conditioning
Hz	hertz
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IPP	independent power producer
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LFP	lithium iron phosphate
MAGPI	Microgrids in Alaska Group: Photovoltaic Integration
NEC	national electric code
NFPA	National Fire Protection Association
O&M	operations and maintenance
RFI	request for information
RFP	request for proposals
SAM	System Advisor Model
TCP	transmission control protocol
VAR	volt-ampere reactive, reactive power measurement

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1. General Planning Considerations

An electric grid should always balance generation and load to keep frequency and voltage within acceptable ranges. Microgrids are electric grids that contain both generation and loads within an electrically isolated boundary. Discussions of microgrids commonly concern grid-connected microgrids, which can connect to and disconnect from a larger power system based on operational criteria. Electric grids in rural Alaska are often permanently isolated microgrids, meaning that they are not connected to larger grids and are, therefore, unable to use large, networked power generators that provide grid-stabilizing inertia. When compared to large grids, such as those in the contiguous United States, Alaska microgrids are much more susceptible to disturbances that can damage equipment and cause safety concerns.

Microgrid components may be configured differently depending on operational situations, which may result in variation in equipment and programming for installation-specific needs. At the outset, a microgrid project should have specific objectives that define what benefits or issues the microgrid project should address. Specific objectives may include economic efficiency, system reliability, system resilience and environmental benefits².

When upgrading an existing microgrid with any new technology, working with good people can be the difference between project failure and success. Inverter-based technologies, such as batteries, solar and wind, can change grid operations considerably. An integrator is a firm or person who analyzes how existing and new equipment will work together on the power system. Integrator services can include anything that supports utility operators in adding new capabilities to power systems, such as financial analysis, system control, planning and operation and maintenance. Developing an integration plan helps keep projects on track and allows utilities to work proactively while adding new capabilities. Continued support from an engaged integrator during the first year of service of any new equipment is critical because the integrator can provide troubleshooting and coordination between vendors.

Installing adequate power quality metering as early as possible in project development ensures that any equipment that is added to the microgrid can ride through and stabilize—and not exacerbate—existing voltage and frequency fluctuations. Large voltage and frequency fluctuations are a common challenge in Alaska microgrids, which are low-inertia and operate on aging equipment.

2. Controller Considerations

To control a microgrid, a control system must be able to sense the state of the microgrid through meters installed at key locations. The controller takes this information and uses it to make decisions about how to operate the grid based on predefined optimization criteria.

² IEEE 2030.9-2019 <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8746836>

Microgrids often include various devices that perform control functions. Controllers can range from device-level controllers that manage the output of a single device within pre-designed limits to system-level energy management systems³.

For permanently islanded microgrids with only diesel engines, a diesel controller may be sufficient to cover diesel-only operations. These device-level controllers are frequently used in Alaska microgrids to operate diesel generators to maintain isochronous frequency and load sharing between paralleled units.

Microgrids that incorporate batteries or renewable resources may require higher-level control functions to be provided by one or several devices, which are incorporated into the microgrid control system. A microgrid may have a system-level controller responsible for maintaining system stability by balancing real-time supply and demand to regulate voltage and frequency. The system-level controller should be capable of bilateral communication with the device-level controllers, such as battery management systems and solar inverters.

Existing grids may include equipment that could provide some control features. An integration plan for adding battery storage and/or renewable energy sources should consider current control capabilities and communication interfaces when considering what equipment to procure.

Many specifications for microgrid controllers are designed for microgrids that are able to operate while tied to a larger grid. Control functions associated with islanding and reconnection may, therefore, be unnecessary for applications in remote Alaska if the microgrid is permanently islanded.

2.1 General Control Functions

Several core control functions should be included in any microgrid to ensure system stability and safety. These functions may be supplied by a higher-level system controller, device-level controllers, or a combination of these, depending on the installation needs.

The microgrid needs to maintain stable frequency and voltage to ensure device protection and customer comfort. Frequency control on small Alaska microgrids may be handled by the isochronous control mode, which may be operated by the diesel device controller. Droop control may be another option for adjusting frequency and voltage.

A microgrid should be able to manage both energy and power to operate autonomously. A control system should be capable of connecting and disconnecting feeders. The controller should only connect a feeder if there is sufficient generation online before connection. In the event of underfrequency or overload conditions, the controller should shed feeders to balance load with generation. Additionally, dispatchable loads, such as batteries and electric boilers, can be used to balance energy and reduce low loading on diesel generators.

The control system may turn off the diesel engines if the battery has sufficient operating reserves and renewables are forecasted to remain high. When a system controller (described in

³ Many of the recommendations in this section draw from IEEE 2030-7.2017 <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8340204>

the next section) is also used, it should provide a sufficient amount of dynamic spinning reserve to the diesel dispatcher, which needs to be kept online.

Additional spinning reserves beyond what is needed to meet the current load may be required to back up variable generation sources, such as wind power. Batteries may be used to provide the spinning reserve for the system, thus reducing the need to run large generators at low loads during high renewable operating conditions.

2.2 Diesel Control Functions

A diesel controller or diesel dispatcher is a device-level controller that manages generator units (e.g., starting, stopping, engine parameters, or basic safety) to ensure generators run safely and efficiently. Diesel generators in Alaska microgrids are typically operated as synchronous generators, meaning that they convert mechanical energy from the diesel engine to electrical energy at the frequency of the grid, which is 60 hertz (Hz) across North America.

AVEC prefers to integrate inverter-based resources, such as batteries, wind and solar, directly with the diesel plant and provide mission-critical control decisions through the existing diesel control schemes.

In AVEC systems, the diesel controllers may maintain isochronous frequency and load sharing between paralleled units. Additionally, the system is designed to decide when generators should be turned off and on to follow the load. Ideally, generator-switching should be kept to a minimum to reduce wear on the generators due to frequent starts and stops. The chosen combination of diesel generators should be the most efficient, and the system should be able to change which generators are on to follow changes in load and renewable energy generation. The diesel dispatcher should consider whether there are any generators out of service so that it can make decisions based on the online units.

The diesel dispatcher may be responsible for feeder connection and shedding for diesel-only microgrids in Alaska.

2.3 System-Level Controllers

Complex grids that incorporate distributed energy resources and renewables require control structures that can sense the state of the entire system and make control decisions accordingly. Although we provide general guidance for programming controllers, the standards required for system performance and setpoints for the controller and devices will need to be determined for each microgrid. IEEE 2030.7-2017⁴ specifies features of microgrid controllers, and IEEE 2030.8-2018⁵ specifies testing procedures to verify these functions.

Some functions of microgrid system controllers, such as transitioning from on-grid to islanded mode, are not typically used in Alaska microgrids that are permanently islanded.

AVEC use of microgrid system controllers

⁴ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8340204>

⁵ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8444947>

AVEC programs its microgrid system controllers in-house because commercial off-the-shelf solutions do not exist for permanently islanded Alaska microgrids⁶. The system controller must consider diverse data sources and make decisions based on the current state of the grid.

AVEC programs its system controllers such that they shall:

- Limit charging and discharging power to extend the life of the battery whenever possible. Maximize battery energy storage system longevity by treating the battery gently whenever possible (i.e., minimizing depth of charge and discharge). Batteries are expensive, and end-of-life disposal considerations for remote Alaska may increase costs relative to installations in other settings.
- Maintain a sufficient battery state of charge to provide sufficient spinning reserve for restarting a diesel generator if required.
- Arbitrage energy by charging the battery when renewables are in excess and discharging when the battery can offset diesel use.
- Prevent battery overcharging.
- Stabilize fluctuations in voltage and frequency when multiple generators are online.
- Decide whether to avoid generator switching by discharging the battery when the diesel load increases to avoid turning on a larger generator or charging the battery when the diesel load decreases to a minimum.
- Decide whether to charge or discharge the battery when a diesel generator is online and operating in the middle of its range.
- Transfer the load away from the diesel generator first when going diesel-off.
- Control voltage and frequency precisely when in diesel-off operation.
- Switch back to diesel-only generation when the battery energy storage system (BESS) is out of service or equalizing.

When renewable energy sources increase, the system controller should follow the priorities listed below to reduce diesel consumption and prepare for a potential shift to diesel-off operations. These points are listed in the order of priority that AVEC considers when programming controllers.

1. Charge the battery to its maximum allowed state of charge when this load is needed to maintain a minimum diesel operating level.
2. When the battery is fully charged, additional excess power should be used to heat the powerhouse.

⁶

https://akml-my.sharepoint.com/:p/g/personal/onedrive_akml_org/EZYwbNS0GIZLv9H9aXBMT9QBOMJ6HNXP5SNc_iCyTsfuw?time=xfRKTNWU3Ug

3. If desired, the last running diesel generator should be turned off.
4. If no more battery charging or powerhouse heating is necessary, renewable sources should be curtailed.
5. Remote interruptible loads can use otherwise curtailed power as long as the powerhouse stays warm enough for the diesel generators to turn back on smoothly.

When available energy from renewables decreases, the system controller should follow these priorities in order:

1. Stop curtailing renewables.
2. Allow the powerhouse heater to shut down and the temperature in the powerhouse to decrease to the minimum desired.
3. Disconnect remote interruptible loads.
4. Restart the diesel generators when the battery charge is sufficiently low.
5. Turn on diesel generators as needed and in a way that reduces wear on the systems.
6. Discharge the batteries somewhat to avoid burning expensive diesel fuel.

3. Inverter Considerations

An inverter turns direct current (DC) power, provided by generation resources, such as batteries, solar and wind, into alternating current (AC) power, which is used to transmit power across an electric grid. As of 2025, most inverters installed worldwide are grid-following, which output current and rely on an existing grid to provide a frequency and voltage setpoint. However, these control schemes can cause positive feedback that may lead to grid instabilities. Furthermore, they may be unsuitable for microgrid applications because of their dependency on another source for synchronization.

To address these challenges, grid-forming (GFM) inverter control schemes can be used to create and feed voltage to the grid. A GFM inverter can operate independently and is necessary to support diesel-off operations on microgrids. Due to its programmable nature, a GFM inverter may be more flexible than traditional synchronous generation sources, such as diesel generators.

The control schemes for GFM inverters are under development, and vendors may not be considering the specific needs of permanently islanded Alaska microgrids. Therefore, continued engagement helps both operators and vendors develop future capabilities. System operators should specify performance-based criteria, validated through a well-defined testing plan, to ensure the successful integration of inverter-based resources onto microgrids.

System-specific requirements should be defined as much as possible at the project-planning phase. An adequate budget should be included to allow for testing, both at the factory acceptance stage and for the site acceptance test. This budget should include travel

funding for vendors to participate in on-site commissioning. The Energy Technology Facility⁷ at ACEP operates as a testing laboratory and can be incorporated into a testing plan.

An inverter should have the demonstrated ability to load share in parallel with a similarly sized diesel generator as part of the factory acceptance test. This ability ensures that the inverter can perform under similar load-sharing conditions to those it will experience onsite.

Appropriately tuned damping parameters ensure that the response of the inverter will not exacerbate voltage and frequency disturbances. Defining parameters similar to those of a similarly sized diesel generator integrated into the microgrid is a good first pass to specify damping parameters for an inverter.

3.1 Modeling Inverters

The need for accurate models increases as grids incorporate higher amounts of inverter-based resources. Models can help utilities anticipate how their systems will respond to contingencies and blackouts and provide the basis for studies for the safe operation of power systems.

The traditional power system is dominated by synchronous machines, where the relevant electromechanical physics are well understood. However, inverter-based resources are becoming more widespread and can operate much more flexibly than traditional synchronous machines. Nevertheless, models must represent the control strategy implemented in the inverter to accurately model the dynamics of inverter-based resources. Vendors may supply specific models for particular equipment. Generic models of inverters with various control strategies are also available.

4. Example Criteria for a Request for Proposal for a Battery Energy Storage System

In this section, we provide an outline for a request for proposal (RFP) developed from one issued by Tanana Chiefs Conference for a BESS and an independent power producer (IPP) controller in September 2025. We also provide recommendations based on conversations with technical experts working on Alaska microgrids.

4.1 General RFP Outline

1. Introduction and project overview: This section should contain high-level information about the location and grid system where the work will take place. High-level requirements for the system should be summarized, including:
 - a. Climatic and weather conditions may be extreme compared to what vendors may be used to. Describe typical weather throughout the year, with an understanding

⁷ <https://www.uaf.edu/acep/facilities/power-systems-integration-laboratory.php>

that these conditions may change over the lifetime of the project to provide context.

- b. Special considerations for the culture and geography of the region where the microgrid system will be installed may also be specified here.
2. Project schedule: An RFP needs a deadline for when to receive applications. There may be many constraints for this, which may derive from internal or external pressures. This section should include expectations for when designs, quotes, testing, construction and commissioning will occur. Examples of schedule constraints are provided below.
 - a. Requiring vendors to meet key milestones ahead of the construction season can minimize delays, particularly for logistically complicated projects. For BESS installations off the road system, the period of availability of different transportation options may be short. Even for those on the road system, preparing for weather-related delays may limit when materials can be safely and/or economically delivered.
 - b. Construction in environmentally sensitive areas (i.e., on tundra or permafrost) may require several years of preparation.
 - c. Heavy equipment may need to be delivered alongside the BESS itself, as the required equipment may be unavailable in the off-road community.
3. Scope of work: The scope of work should identify who is responsible for what aspect of the project. At the start, it is good practice to establish who will be responsible for delivering various aspects of the project to facilitate progress and reduce liability for contractors and project owners. Aspects of the work to consider detailing at the proposal stage include, but are not limited to:
 - a. Project planning and design: Some high-level project objectives may need to be defined to specify aspects of the project design.
 - b. Permitting and regulatory approvals: Many locations in Alaska are environmentally sensitive. Transporting materials and installing projects may require special permits.
 - c. Site preparation: This includes aspects such as clearing the land where the project will be installed and ensuring that electrical equipment can physically connect to the grid.
 - d. Materials and equipment procurement, including compliance with any grant-funded requirements: These may include compliance with the Build America, Buy America Act, local hiring requirements, and federal contracting preferences.
 - e. Shipping: Shipping to remote communities may involve complicated plans and require materials be sent in by barge months ahead of time. There may also be restrictions dependent on the transport companies operating in the region.

- f. Installation: Identify unique installation features that may require aspects of the project to be completed when the ground is frozen.
 - g. Interconnection.
 - h. Programming: AVEC prefers to program its own microgrid control systems; however, this could alternately be handled by the controller vendor, the project integrator, or a trusted contractor.
 - i. Environmental and safety compliance: Depending on the landowner, federal permitting requirements, wildlife habitat restrictions and other environmental and safety compliance measures may need to be considered.
 - j. Commissioning: Having a vendor on site during the commissioning test is highly recommended.
 - k. Project management.
 - l. Developing standard operating procedures.
 - m. Operator training: What will the trained operator be responsible for, and how will they receive the necessary training?
 - n. Warranty: How will warranty recalls be handled when a system is in a remote location and backhaul options are limited? Manufacturers may be wary about offering warranty support for temperatures below -40 °F or even -20 °F; however, these temperatures are a reality in Alaska.
 - o. Ownership.
 - p. Quality control: Device tests should be performed before installation.
 - q. Operations and maintenance: A good operations and maintenance (O&M) plan is essential for long-term project success.
 - r. Post-installation support.
4. Use case: The use case for the BESS system should be defined early in the project. Different use cases will have varying economic and technical requirements, which will define high-level objectives.
 5. Expected duration at full battery discharge capacity: A range of two to four hours of storage, given battery life constraints around state of charge, is standard for grid-tied installations in the contiguous United States. Shorter durations may be used for different applications, such as the design of grid-bridging systems that enable diesel generators off operation. Preliminary economic modeling with a tool such as HOMER (Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources) or SAM (System Advisor Model) may help determine the cost-optimal size of the battery.

6. Expected cycles: They will depend on the project-specific use case and economics. One cycle per day on average is a good assumption for a diesel-off enabled bridging system. Programming the battery and microgrid controllers may limit the state of charge fluctuations to maximize battery lifespan.
7. Thermal management: Batteries need to be kept within their safe operating range.
8. Cell chemistry: Lithium iron phosphate (LFP) batteries are relatively safe, long-lived (keeping costs low over time), and have high energy and power density (reducing shipping costs for a given project size). Hence, they may work for many Alaska-specific microgrid applications. Other battery chemistries that meet the required specifications may be considered. Note that “Made in America” requirements for some federal grant-funded projects may limit the availability of certain technologies.
9. Round-trip efficiency: This refers to the efficiency of the entire system, including the battery, its management system (i.e., HVAC), and any losses associated with charging and discharging. Higher is better. Eighty-five percent round-trip efficiency is an adequate target in 2025; however, issuing a request for information (RFI) before an RFP can help you determine what efficiencies are available from manufacturers.
10. Useful economic life: This may be determined by what vendors are willing to commit to and will be project-specific. At the end of the useful economic life, the battery will have degraded, and components may need to be repaired or replaced. Thus, a modular design that allows for easy repairs can extend the true lifespan of a project.
11. Outside temperature range: This is site-specific. Manufacturers may be wary about offering warranty support for temperatures below -40°F or even -20°F , which many places in Alaska experience. Vendors who can work with expected climatological temperature ranges are required for project success in Alaska. Additionally, temperatures above 100°F may be expected over the economic life of the project.
12. Building requirements: The BESS will need housing to keep it safe from the outside conditions. Equipment that can be easily and cheaply erected in rural Alaska is typically modular and standardized (i.e., weatherized Conex or prefab metal structures). Expectations for the mechanical load on the building (i.e., wind or snow) should be specified here.
13. Fire safety: NFPA 101 (Life Safety Code) and NFPA 5000 (Building Safety Code) should be a minimum level of compliance for the battery housing. Water-based fire suppression may be inadequate in Alaska because of the potential for freezing temperatures. Interior and exterior, audible and visible alarms should be present to ensure worker safety under all conditions.
14. Shipping restrictions: These depend on the specific transport companies operating in the region. Battery modules may have a maximum weight determined by the availability of local heavy machinery or transportation requirements. As of 2025, some barge companies are not shipping lithium batteries.

15. HVAC requirements: The battery needs to be kept at an optimal temperature and humidity for long-lasting operations. These systems may have substantial power requirements that can make projects less economical to operate. Information on the power draw associated with these systems should be requested as part of an RFP so that the economics of the project can be accurately determined.
16. Battery management system: It monitors all aspects of the battery required to safely operate the BESS with existing systems.
17. Codes and standards: Equipment may be required to meet certain standards. See Part 5 for more information.
18. Quality assurance: Any requirements for the performance of the BESS and contractor should be specified. Testing at the factory and on site can help anticipate potential problems. AVEC and TCC developed a preliminary testing plan for batteries⁸. IEEE 2030.8-2018 defines controller testing standards; however, many of the test functions are for grid-tied installations⁹.
19. Site commissioning: Having a BESS vendor participate in site acceptance testing is best practice. The budget should provide for vendor travel to the site where the BESS will be installed.

4.2 Inverter/BESS Criteria Recommendations

These criteria have been adapted from MAGPI recommendations and a review of several RFPs issued for far-northern, remote power systems. Additionally, Bill Thomson and Aimie Survant from AVEC publicly presented on this topic with Mari Shirazi from ACEP at a Universal Interoperability for Grid-Forming Inverters seminar, which was recorded and is available on YouTube¹⁰.

The recommendations below are a starting point and may not be ideal in every situation. A professional engineer can help build an RFP suited for the specific installation.

- **Must have grid-forming capability:** Inverters should operate in grid-forming (GFM) mode all the time, as switching or operating in grid-following (GFL) mode can create problems. Additionally, the GFM mode can provide additional grid services and support grid stability, whereas the GFL mode can create instability. AVEC requires all inverters to have the GFM mode. Communications delays can cause an observable light flicker when an inverter is operating in the GFL mode and load-sharing with a diesel generator.
- **Four-wire connections:** Inverters shall be capable of four-wire connections (neutral support). Inverters that connect directly to power plants shall be four-wire.

⁸

<https://www.tananachiefs.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/Attachment-E-BESS-Testing-Requirements.pdf>

⁹ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8444947>

¹⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WI3pc4Xv_9E&ab_channel=UNIFIconsortium

- No isolation transformers: Inverters shall not require an isolation transformer because the expense, lead times, and losses associated with transformers are unacceptable when their only function is isolation. AVEC requires that all inverters can connect to the grid without an isolation transformer.
- Faster balancing/equalizing of batteries: All inverters shall be able to balance cells continuously as required during normal operation, thus reducing the necessary downtime for occasional off-line full-charge balancing. Furthermore, AVEC requires details on equalization methods before purchase.
- Adjustable inertia: All inverters shall have an easily adjustable inertia setting when in GFM mode. AVEC requires that the inertia-constant H be adjustable within the range of 2 to 20 seconds.
- Adjustable dampening: All inverters shall have an easily adjustable dampening setting when operating in the GFM mode.
- Adjustable frequency droop: All inverters shall have an easily adjustable range of frequency droop settings. AVEC expects a 0.5 to 2.0 Hz droop rate for a change of 100% rated power.
- Adjustable voltage droop: All inverters shall have an easily adjustable range of voltage droop settings. AVEC expects between 2% and 5% droop for a change of 100% rated reactive power.
- Power and frequency control via frequency setpoint: All inverters shall be capable of Hz setpoint control when operating in the GFM mode. AVEC expects a minimum +/- 2 Hz control range.
- Reactive power (VAR) and voltage control via voltage setpoint: All inverters shall be capable of voltage setpoint control when operating in the GFM mode. The system controller will typically adjust the inverter setpoint to minimize VAR output from the inverters when paralleled with the diesel gensets. AVEC expects a minimum +/- 10% adjustment range.
- System control interface: All inverters must be controllable by an energy and power balancing controller. This control system may be owned by the electric utility or an IPP, depending on project architecture. If the controller is owned and operated by an IPP, it must be able to communicate and be interoperable with other control devices in the system. AVEC provides a system controller for wind installations. AVEC currently requires Modbus over transmission control protocol (TCP) capability for communications. This setup can avoid locking a system into a proprietary vendor system. Additional cybersecurity protocols and controls will be needed for remote power system monitoring and control.
- Inverter arrays: These are valued for ease of maintenance and redundancy. Inverter arrays must stay synchronized with each other despite charging setpoints and without losses due to recirculating currents.

- Direct power plant connectivity: Inverters shall be able to directly connect to diesel power plants without harmonic issues.
- Factory acceptance testing: Inverters shall be factory-tested before shipment, using approved, witnessed, or certified testing procedures. Tests for both GFM and GFL modes, while paralleled and not paralleled with another generation source, shall be included in the test plan. The inverter shall be tested to ensure it maintains continuous power quality in case a paralleled generation source is lost when running at full rated capacity.
- Inverter capacity: The inverter will usually be sized based on peak system load (winter peak), so that the inverter can pick up the entire system if suddenly required.
- Battery capacity: The power capacity from the battery must be sufficient to match the inverter capacity at the end of life. AVEC prefers to know the marginal cost of additional energy storage to optimize the economics of the battery purchase.
- Identify and minimize parasitic losses: High operating consumption can make a project uneconomical due to the high marginal cost of generation in AVEC communities.
- Droop, do not trip if possible: The inverter shall droop the frequency before tripping if the BESS is overloaded. This provides time for frequency-sensitive protection to perform load shedding, avoiding blackout conditions during grid disturbances.
- Automatic curtailment when communications are lost: The inverter shall cease to energize when communications are lost.

5. Standards

Standards provide an external description of quality control. Equipment and contractors may be required to meet certain standards to ensure a certain level of performance and quality. Standards are frequently updated and represent the consensus of technical experts and practitioners at the time they were written. Procuring equipment that adheres to certain standards can guarantee a level of interoperability with future technology.

However, the downside to requiring that equipment adhere to standards is that certification may come with an added cost, particularly for newer or less commonly used standards. Reviewing standards may help develop RFP language. The dates on standards should be noted because older standards may not represent current best practices.

Some standards to consider in an RFP include:

1. IEEE 1547¹¹: In 2018, this standard was updated to include enhanced interconnection requirements for distributed energy resources. This standard requires that equipment can

¹¹ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1547/5915/>

ride through many different grid disturbances, which may cause noncompliant equipment to trip offline. ACEP hosted a two-day workshop on IEEE 1547 as part of the 2025 Alaska Sustainable Energy Conference. Recordings of the two sessions are available on YouTube¹².

2. 2021 International Building Code¹³: This standard provides minimum requirements for buildings, which may be needed if a battery system is to be housed in its own structure.
3. NFPA 70 (NEC)¹⁴: The National Electric Code ensures that all electrical installations follow best safety practices to protect people and property. As of 2025, Alaska requires adherence to the 2020 version of NFPA 70 for all electrical installations.
 - 3.1. NFPA 70E describes worker and workplace safety standards.
4. NFPA 855¹⁵: This standard provides requirements that minimize the hazards of energy storage systems.
5. UL 1741: UL provides safety standards for various electrical products and testing protocols to determine whether products meet the standards. Official UL certification requires a series of tests by a certified facility. UL 1740 is the Standard for Inverters, Converters, Controllers and Interconnection System Equipment for Use with Distributed Energy Resources¹⁶.
 - 5.1. UL 1741SA supplements UL 1741 to provide requirements for inverters that have functions that can support the grid through disturbances.
6. UL 1973: This standard—the Standard for Batteries for Use in Stationary, Vehicle Auxiliary Power and Light Electric Rail (LER) Applications—provides criteria for determining whether batteries meet certain safety requirements. Like other UL standards, adherence to this standard requires that equipment be tested according to certain criteria in a certified facility.
7. UL 9540: The Standard for Energy Storage Systems and Equipment provides criteria for the overall safety of energy storage systems, covering electrical, mechanical, environmental and functional safety. NFPA 855 mandates adherence to UL 9540.
 - 7.1. Adherence to UL 9540A may be required for large battery installations. This standard describes how energy storage systems respond to thermal runaway events.
8. IEC 62485¹⁷: This standard describes safety requirements for the installation, use, inspection, maintenance and disposal of rechargeable lithium BESS.
9. IEC 62909¹⁸: This standard describes general and safety requirements for bidirectional grid-connected power converters, which consist of an inverter connected to one or more DC ports. The DC port may be attached to a bidirectional (i.e., can charge and discharge) energy storage system, such as a battery.

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oGk8NHvYWdQ>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8TSkQoegOPc>

¹³ <https://codes.iccsafe.org/content/IBC2021V2.0>

¹⁴ <https://www.nfpa.org/codes-and-standards/nfpa-70-standard-development/70>

¹⁵ <https://www.nfpa.org/codes-and-standards/nfpa-855-standard-development/855>

¹⁶ <https://www.ul.com/news/ul-launches-advanced-inverter-testing-and-certification-program>

¹⁷ <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/29086>

¹⁸ <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/69114>

10. IEC 62619¹⁹: This standard describes requirements and tests for the safe operation of lithium batteries that can be charged and discharged.
11. IEC 62933-5-2²⁰: This standard describes safety requirements for electrical energy storage systems.
12. IEC 62477-1²¹: This standard describes safety requirements for power electronic converter systems, which cover power electronics-based inverters.
13. IEEE 519²²: This standard describes how electrical systems should meet minimum requirements for voltage and current distortion. Existing grids may need to be updated to meet these standards before interconnecting inverter-based resources.
14. IEEE 693²³: Recommended practice for the seismic design of substations. This standard may be necessary based on the seismic hazards of the installation's location.
15. IFC 1207²⁴: Standard for fire safety set by the International Fire Code.
16. ISO 14001²⁵: This standard describes how an organization can implement an environmental management system intended to mitigate the ecological footprint of activities.
17. ISO 8528-1: This is a standard for reciprocating internal combustion engine-driven AC generating sets. Several tables defining performance categories and engine parameters are available and can be the basis for scoping a potential inverter that performs like a diesel generator.
18. IEEE 2030.9²⁶: IEEE-recommended practices for the planning and design of microgrids.

¹⁹ <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/64073>

²⁰ <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/32177>

²¹ <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/28936>

²² <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/519/10677/>

²³ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/693/4996/>

²⁴ <https://codes.iccsafe.org/s/IFC2024P1/chapter-12-energy-systems/IFC2024P1-Pt03-Ch12-Sec1207>

²⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/60857.html>

²⁶ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8746836>